

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE QUALITIES BASED ON THE SCIENTIFIC AND PHILOSOPHICAL HERITAGE OF EASTERN THINKERS

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Abstract. In our country, a lot of reforms are being carried out by the educational system management bodies in order to achieve high indicators of educational processes in general education institutions. The formation and development of students as creative individuals depends on the mutual compatibility of changes in their internal and external world, socio-economic conditions, and the implementation of tasks aimed at increasing their creative qualities in educational processes. These practical activities create the need for students to achieve new achievements, move forward to a certain extent, help to develop their learning abilities to some extent.

Key words: educational system, students, creativity, creative qualities, creative ability, pedagogical thinking, creative environment, creative thinking, creativity, personal creativity qualities.

Introduction. The future of every society is determined by the level of development of its education system, which is its integral part and vital necessity. Today, as our country moves along the path of independent development, the fundamental reform and improvement of the continuous education system, its elevation to a new qualitative level, the introduction of advanced pedagogical and information technologies into it, and the improvement of educational efficiency have risen to the level of state policy. In particular, the adoption of the new edition of the Law “On Education” [1] is evidence of the fact that special attention is being paid to educating students who are comprehensively developed, who can compete with the youth of

the most developed countries of the world, and who can think creatively through the continuous education system.

The Decree of our Honorable President No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 “On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026” [2] and other regulatory and legal documents related to this area set out priority tasks aimed at improving the education system and thereby forming the creative qualities of students and young people.

In our republic, it is urgent to organize educational processes in all general education institutions based on the requirements of the time, to introduce the most advanced innovative technologies into them, and thereby achieve the quality and efficiency of education. In this regard, the issue of developing strategies and tools that serve to develop the creative qualities of students, stimulate creative thinking and the results of creative activity is of particular importance. First of all, let us explain the concept of “Creativity”. Creativity (lat., eng. “create” - to create, “creative” - creator, creator) is a creative ability that characterizes the readiness of an individual to produce new ideas and is part of giftedness as an independent factor.

A person’s creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activity. Creativity characterizes a person as a whole or its specific features. Creativity is also reflected as an important factor of giftedness. Creativity also determines mental acuity and ensures the active involvement of students in the educational process.

- Analysis of the literature on the topic. In recent years, special attention has been paid to the formation and development of creative qualities in students in the educational systems of developed foreign countries. In particular, this can be seen in many studies conducted by scientists such as Merryman (2010), Bronson, Fisher, Frey (2008), Ken Robinson (2007), Begetto, Kaufman (2013), Ali (2011), Treffinger (2008). According to Ken Robinson, “creativity is a set of original ideas that have their own value.” Gardner, in his research, explains this concept as follows: “creativity is a practical action carried out by a person, which must reflect a certain novelty and have a certain practical value.” According to Emebiel (1989), creativity is “the acquisition of highly unusual skills in a specific field, combined with thorough knowledge” [3].

Some studies have divergent views on the relationship between intelligence and creativity. While some researchers argue that there is no relationship between them, others argue that creativity and intelligence are related. The concept of “creativity” reflects cultural diversity. For Westerners, creativity is generally considered to be a novelty. They emphasize that creativity is based on unconventionality, curiosity, imagination, a sense of humor, and freedom (Murdoch and Ganim, 1993; Sternberg, 1985). Easterners, on the other hand, understand creativity as a process of rebirth of goodness (Hui, Sternberg, 2002; Rudovich, Hui, 1997; Rudovich, Yue, 2000). Although Westerners and Easterners have different views on creativity, both cultures highly value this quality and its possession (Kaufman, Lan, 2012) [3].

- Research methodology. Like any other quality (virtue), creativity is not formed at once. Creativity is developed consistently at certain stages. So, when do creative traits manifest themselves in a person's activity? Usually, creativity is often observed in children's activities, but this does not guarantee that children will achieve creative achievements in the future. It only indicates the likelihood that they will need to master one or another creative skill or competence. When developing creativity in children, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

- 1) encourage them to ask a lot of questions and support this habit;
- 2) encourage children's independence and increase their responsibility;
- 3) create opportunities for children to organize independent activities;
- 4) focus on children's interests

Researcher N. Fayzullaeva believes that in order to have a pedagogical mindset, students need to be able to master the following skills and competencies based on thorough study of pedagogical knowledge: knowledge of the main ideas, concepts, laws of pedagogy and the laws of development of pedagogical phenomena; knowledge of the most important theoretical ideas, main categories and concepts of pedagogy; knowledge of basic pedagogical facts; acquisition of practical knowledge about the general method of education and upbringing [4].

In psychology, E.P. Torrens developed a test to determine a person's creativity. According to E.P. Torrens, a person's creativity manifests itself in the following signs:

- a) not ignoring questions, shortcomings, and contradictory information;
- b) trying to identify problems and find solutions based on the assumptions put forward.

According to many scientists, before forming creative thinking skills in students, it is necessary to create a favorable creative environment in the classroom. Students who are educated in a creative environment gradually increase their interest and motivation in performing creative tasks, and also tend to think creatively as a result of observing a teacher with creative thinking. A learning environment characterized by creativity leads to the development of critical and creative thinking skills in students, which are of great importance in the educational process [5].

The characteristics of creative learners are:

- they express ideas that other learners would not have thought of;
- they choose their own style of expression; sometimes ask unrelated or unusual questions;
- they enjoy open-ended tasks; prefer to discuss ideas based on concrete evidence;
- they choose an unconventional approach to solving a problem.

The following figure shows the qualities of creativity in a person [3]:

As mentioned above, creative qualities in students do not develop on their own. Accordingly, research has highlighted a number of ways to successfully develop creative qualities in an individual. Patti Drepeau [5] has shown four ways to successfully develop creative qualities in an individual (Figure 2):

There are factors that prevent students from developing creative qualities and skills. Therefore, teachers should pay attention to eliminating these factors in the educational process.

The following factors prevent the development of creativity in an individual:

- 1) avoiding taking risks;
- 2) allowing rudeness in thinking and behavior;
- 3) undervaluing one's fantasy and imagination;
- 4) subordination to others;
- 5) thinking only about success in any situation.

In general education institutions, teachers should be able to create the necessary conditions for students to work in teams, small or large groups, in order to form and develop creative thinking skills. After all, in the process of working in large and small groups, there is an opportunity to creatively develop any idea expressed. According to scientists, the teacher, recognizing the importance of a sense of team spirit, constantly changes groups in creativity lessons, thereby forming in students the ability to work as a team, respect the abilities and skills of others. However, if working individually is effective in certain situations, it is advisable to work in small groups in creativity lessons, because the skill of creativity is a social phenomenon. In particular, according to Soyer, creative views are formed in the process of working in a team and as a result of creative cooperation.

- Analysis and results. In order to teach students to think creatively and to form creative thinking in them, the teacher must first of all have a creative mind and be a creative person. If he does not have the qualities of creativity himself, he cannot encourage students to think creatively. In the lessons, the teacher moves in the following 4 directions according to the “creativity roadmap”, and the actions in them are considered signs of the creativity of teachers:

1) demonstrating creative thinking skills; 2) being able to use strategies that encourage students to master academic subjects with interest; 3) an innovative approach and a creative approach to finding solutions to pedagogical issues;

Conclusions and suggestions. In conclusion, it can be said that identifying, forming and developing creative abilities in students will help them grow into well-rounded, broad-minded, and worldly-minded people in the future. For this, it is not necessary for the teacher to be creative or not, but to organize lessons in the spirit of creativity and strive to test new ideas in the educational process.

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